

1 **Xist exerts deleterious, oncogenic function in AML.**

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6 We previously described activation of Xist following loss of the tumor suppressors p53 and Rb1 in
7 solid tissues in mouse and man, and a role for Xist in lineage specification of breast cancer molecular
8 subtype (1-5). Contrarily, Xist has been described as a tumor suppressor in hematopoietic stem cells (6).
9 We found robust activation of Xist in acute myeloid leukemia. Survey of human cancers demonstrated
10 that like in breast cancer, Xist is over-expressed in AML. Consistent with a model wherein Xist activation
11 is deleterious (oncogenic or mutator type [7]), increased AML expression correlated with inferior overall
12 survival (decreased time to death) - in males but not females. Interestingly, Xist expression cooperated
13 with NPM1 mutation or mutation of the tyrosine kinase domain of FLT3 to influence survival of humans
14 with AML. Xist is not likely to possess tumor suppressor function in at least one hematologic cancer, or
15 alternatively, its oncogenic or tumor suppressive function changes throughout transformation and disease
16 progression in the hematopoietic compartment.
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Results

We surveyed total Xist expression comparing tumor and normal tissues in 22 cancers.

Figure 1: Xist is over-expressed in AML.

Xist was expressed at relatively high levels in AML, and the range of Xist expression in AML was quite large.

We used a large patient cohort to study relationships between tumor cell expression of Xist in AML and overall patient survival (time to death).

Figure 2: In males but not females with AML, Xist expression correlates with inferior overall survival.

When considering all patients together, Xist appears to exert a positive influence on overall survival in humans with AML (Figure 2; left; consider two separate probe sets for Xist survival analysis). When considering males with AML separately, the oncogenic influence of Xist on patient overall survival is obvious (Figure 2; center). [When considering females with AML separately, the broad influence of Xist on human gene expression in transformation in a sex-specific fashion is apparent (Figure 2; right).

We then studied overall survival of humans with AML based on presence of cooperative oncogenic mutation, finding strong survival phenotypes for Xist cooperation with oncogenic background in patients with the NPM1 mutation and in patients with the FLT3 tyrosine kinase mutation.

Figure 3: In AML patients with the NPM1 mutation, Xist cooperates with the oncogenic mutation to exert a negative influence on overall survival.

A clear relationship between high expression of the Xist non-coding RNA and decreased time to death (overall survival, or OS) was evident in AML patients with the NPM1 mutation.

Figure 4: In AML patients with FLT3 tyrosine kinase mutation, Xist exerts a positive influence on overall survival.

Contrarily, we found a positive relationship between high expression of the Xist non-coding RNA and time to death in AML patients with the NPM1 mutation.

Thus, Xist was expressed at high levels in AML; in males, Xist influenced an oncogenic-type influence on overall survival; the oncogenic force Xist exerted on disease progression was dependent on genetic background in AML; high Xist expression correlated with decreased OS in patients with NPM1 mutant AML, but in patients with FLT3 TK mutant AML, high Xist expression correlated with increased OS.

1 **References**

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